

**POSTOPERATIVE CARE OF PATIENTS AFTER
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Qualifications of Medical Workers****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20343741>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 17th May 2026Accepted: 19th May 2026Online: 21st May 2026**KEYWORDS**

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ABSTRACT

Therefore, consistent and rational postoperative rehabilitation measures, involving related specialists, play a crucial role in preventing these complications. Based on the course of the postoperative period and the sequence of treatment and preventive measures, we have developed an algorithm for postoperative patient care aimed at restoring impaired bodily functions and consolidating the achieved anatomical, functional, and aesthetic results. The developed algorithm consisted of three stages.

According to scientific literature, up to 40% of complications encountered during various stages of orthognathic treatment for patients with jaw deformities occur in the postoperative period. Therefore, consistent and rational postoperative rehabilitation measures, involving related specialists, play a crucial role in preventing these complications. Based on the course of the postoperative period and the sequence of treatment and preventive measures, we have developed an algorithm for postoperative patient care aimed at restoring impaired bodily functions and consolidating the achieved anatomical, functional, and aesthetic results. The developed algorithm consisted of three stages. The first stage is called the immediate postoperative period, which lasts from 1 to 3 days and involves the patient's stay in intensive care. During this period, the orthognathic surgeon and anesthesiologist/resuscitator are required, where all their efforts should be focused on restoring vital bodily functions. The second stage is called the period of intermaxillary immobilization and lasts from 4 to 8 weeks. This period involved the participation of an orthognathic surgeon, an orthopedic dentist, an orthodontist, and, if indicated, a psychologist. All efforts by the specialists were aimed at preventing inflammatory complications, maintaining the achieved jaw position, and ensuring adequate perception of the altered facial aesthetic balance by the patients. The third stage, called the period of restoration of maxillofacial function, lasts from six months to one year, during which the participation of an orthognathic surgeon, an orthodontist, a general practitioner, and a dental orthopedist was required. During this period, oral hygiene measures, physiotherapy procedures, and drug treatment aimed at optimizing reparative bone regeneration were carried out, as well as continuation of orthodontic treatment initiated before surgery and prosthetic repair of dental defects. The developed algorithm was used in the postoperative rehabilitation of 64 patients

with combined jaw deformities operated on at the Maxillofacial Surgery Clinic of the Central Research and Clinical Orthodontics Center for Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery (CRPCMR) for GBN^o7 from 2018 to 2022. Of the total number, 48 had a concave facial type caused by lower macrognathia or a combination with upper micrognathia, and 16 had a convex facial type caused by lower micrognathia or a combination with upper promacrognathia. Long-term follow-up periods ranged from 1 to 4 years. In the postoperative period, inflammatory processes were observed in two patients. In one case, bone suture rejection with suppuration was observed. In the second case, it was the suture material that suppurated (3.12%). After revision of the abscess, removal of the bone suture, and medical treatment, the inflammatory processes were eliminated by secondary wound intention. One patient experienced an incomplete relapse of lower macrognathia deformity (1.56%) due to failure to perform planned orthodontic treatment after surgery. The minimal incidence of postoperative inflammatory complications and recurrence of jaw deformities, compared to literature data, demonstrates the advantages of the developed algorithm for postoperative rehabilitation of patients with jaw deformities.

